

A Convenient and Exclusive Methoxybromination of Alkenes^{1,2}

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Various alkenes have been exclusively methoxybrominated with bromine in methanol in the presence of a suitable trapping agent for bromide ion such as silver nitrate, lead nitrate, or yellow lead oxide depending on the nature of alkenes. Likewise, a few representative alkenes have also been methoxyiodinated with iodine in methanol in the presence of silver nitrate. Electrophilic addition of the elements of methylhypobromite to alkenes has been shown to be general. The *trans* and stereospecific nature has been established by studying dehydrobromination of methoxybromo adducts under E₂-elimination conditions. The ir and nmr spectra of methoxyhalo adducts and dehydrobrominated products have been recorded and reaction mechanism has been discussed briefly.

THE reaction of bromine in methanol with an alkene generally leads to a mixture of dibromo and methoxybromo adducts^{3,4}. A few isolated examples have been reported in the literature⁵⁻⁷ wherein the exclusive methoxybromination has been observed by making use of yellow lead oxide. Also, Caserio and coworkers⁸ have used silver tetrafluoroborate for stereospecific methoxyiodination of 2,3-pentadiene only. But the generality of the process has not been explored and definite proof has not been reported for the stereochemistry of the addition products. Because methoxybromides themselves are excellent synthetic intermediates and to synthesise them by other alternative routes such as via-N-bromosuccinimide in methanol⁹⁻¹¹ or by methoxymercuration method¹⁰⁻¹⁶ of alkenes with mercuric acetate in methanol followed by treatment with potassium bromide is either a more expensive process or it involves 2-3 separate experimental steps. We, therefore, wished to explore the generality of methoxy-bromination of alkenes with bromine in methanol in the presence of a trapping agent, since this will provide a cheaper and more efficient route to methoxybromo adducts. Further, we desired to ascertain the stereochemistry of the addition products and therefore of methoxy-bromination reaction itself. This paper reports our results in both these areas.

Results and Discussion

The methoxybromination of a variety of alkenes (I) led to exclusive formation of methoxybromo adducts (II) in good to excellent yields (Table I.) The products (II) were characterised by their m.p., b.p. (Table 1), ir and nmr spectra (Table 2). The unknown compounds were also analysed (Table 3). As it is clear from Table 2, the ir spectrum is transparent in the olefinic region and a very characteristic band in the region 2815-2833cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric C-H stretching in the ethereal methoxy group and strong band in the region 1162-1100 cm⁻¹ due to C-O-C bending deformation, characteristic of the ether linkage, were observed. The nmr spectra are consistent with assigned structures (II). It is pertinent

to point out that the ir and nmr spectra for crude and purified samples of II (a,d,f,i,j,l, m and o) in each case were superimposable. This fact itself proves that only one diastereomer was formed in these cases.

The most interesting feature of methoxybromination reaction is esterification of the free carboxylic acid group present in alkenes I (c, e, g and h). Thus in these cases we have been able to accomplish methoxybromination of olefinic linkage and esterification of the carboxylic acid group in "one-flask" step in the presence of lead nitrate or silver nitrate. Esterification does not occur in the presence of yellow lead oxide. It is quite conceivable that nitric acid generated *in situ* catalyses the esterification of the carboxylic acid group. The reaction of prop-2-enoic acid (Ih) results into a mixture of methyl 2-bromo-3-methoxypropanoate (IIh-i)¹⁹ and methyl 3-bromo-2-methoxypropanoate (IIh-ii) in the relative ratio of 64:36 as determined by glc using the columns A and B. The structure for IIh-i and IIh-ii has been assigned on the basis of analysis and their ir and nmr spectra. Methylene protons in IIh-i will be expected to show a little downfield chemical shift (δ 3.70 in Table 2) in comparison to those of the compound IIh-ii (δ 3.59) because C-3 is being bonded to more electronegative oxygen of ethereal methoxy group. Similar arguments led to assign δ -values for other protons in both the positional isomers IIh-i and IIh-ii. Due to steric factor for incoming nucleophile methanol at C-2 and electrostatic repulsion between C-1 and C-2, the bromonium ion ring opening at C-2 appears to be energetically less favourable. Therefore, the ratio of the isomer IIh-ii is only 36%.

Electron-rich alkenes react faster and give much better yield of methoxybromo adducts II (Table 1). The

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TABLE 1—METHOXYHALO ADDUCTS (II)

Alkene (I)	Methoxyhalo Adducts (II)→						† (a,b,c)	Ref.	Temp(°C)	Time(hr)	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	X	% Yield					M.P./B.P°
Ia	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	COOCH ₃	Br	95	—	a	—	25	6
Ib(i)	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOCH ₃	H	Br	98	71-72.5	a, b, c,	3	25	6
(ii)	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOCH ₃	H	Bi	90	68-69	c	4	25	16
Ic(i)*	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOCH ₃	H	Bi	98	71-72.5	b, c	3	25	9
(ii)	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOH	H	Br	84	170-171	c	4	25	16
Id	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	COOCH ₃	H	Br	98	65-66	b	—	25	48
Ie*	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	COOCH ₃	H	Br	82	65-66	b, c	—	25	20
If	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	COOCH ₃	H	Br	98	70-71	b	—	25	20
Ig*	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	COOCH ₃	H	Br	84	70-71	b, c	—	25	96
Ih(i)*	H	H	H	COOCH ₃	Br } Br }	87	60-141/5mm	c	19	-15	2
(ii)	COOCH ₃	H	H	H	Br }						
Ii	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	COCH ₃	Br	89	59-60/3mm	b	—	25	2
Ij	C ₆ H ₅	H	COCH ₃	H	Br	79	114-119/2-3mm	b	20	25	2
Ik	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	H	Br	91	83-84/2.5mm	a, b, c,	12	-10	1
Il	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	Br	94	87-88	a	—	0	20
Im	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	Br	74	118-120	a	3,22	25	20
In	C ₆ H ₅	H	NO ₂	H	Br	10	115-116/3mm	b	21	65	27
Io	(i) <i>trans</i> -1-Bromo-2-methoxycyclohexane					80	48-48.5/0.5mm	c	9,10	-7	5
	(ii) <i>trans</i> -1-Iodo-2-methoxycyclohexane					76	41-43/0.5mm	c	23	-17	½

* The alkenes I (c, e, g and h) are the corresponding carboxylic acid.

† a = Yellow Lead Oxide (PbO); b = Lead Nitrate; c = Silver Nitrate.

electron-poor alkene such as it afforded only 10% yield of the product IIn, the rest being the starting alkene In. This fact appears consistent with electrophilic addition of bromine to alkene leading to true bromonium or bromocarbenium ion intermediate.

This reaction was also extended to iodine instead of bromine but only with silver nitrate as the trapping agent. The results for a few representative alkenes I (b, c and o) have been included in Table 1 and 2.

Mechanism

The results of methoxybromination and methoxyiodination could easily be rationalised on the basis of highly polar transition state III. Analogous transition state IV has been proposed by Garnier, Donnay and Dubois^{2,4} based on the analysis of the secondary solvent isotope effect and on the solvent effect in methanol-water mixture on the rate of bromination of pent-1-ene. In the transition state III, when bromide ion gets precipitated out the only nucleophilic species left behind is

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA FOR COMPOUNDS (II)

II	I.R. Spectra (cm ⁻¹)	N.M.R. Spectra (δ)*
a	3025(w), 2949(m), 2825(m), 1750(vs), 1450(m), 1430(m), 1350(m), 1145(s) and 1106 (s).	3.13(3H,s,OCH ₃), 3.41(3H,s,COOCH ₃), 3.66(1H,d,J=13Hz,C-2 methine), 4.53(1H,d,J=13Hz,C-3 methine) and 7.31(5H,s, aromatic).
b-i, c-i	3025(w), 2950(m), 2815(m), 1750(vs), 1450(m), 1430(m), 1350(m), 1140(s) and 1100(s).	3.21(3H,s,OCH ₃), 3.82(3H,s,COOCH ₃), 4.14(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-2 methine), 4.54(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-3 methine) and (5H,s, aromatic).
b-ii	3055(w), 3025(w), 2950(m), 2820(m), 1750(vs), 1450 (m), 1432(m), 1162(s), 1150(s) and 1090(s)	3.12(3H,s,OCH ₃), 3.68(3H,s,COOCH ₃), 4.47(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-2 methine), 5.26(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-3 methine) and 7.20(5H,s, aromatic).
d, e	3025(w), 3000(w), 2950(m), 2925(m), 2815(m), 1750(vs), 1137(s) and 1100(s).	2.34(3H,s, <i>p</i> -CH ₃), 3.16(3H,s,OCH ₃), 3.80(3H,s,COOCH ₃), 4.06(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-2 methine), 4.46(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-3 methine) and 7.17(4H,s, aromatic).
f, g	3020(w), 2950(m), 2815(m), 1750(vs), 1145(s), 1100(s) and 1085(s).	3.22(3H,s,OCH ₃), 3.83(3H,s,COOCH ₃), 4.07(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-2 methine), 4.52(1H,d,J=10Hz,C-3 methine) and 7.39 (4H,s, aromatic).
h-i	2990(m), 2950(m), 2925(m), 2827(m), 1755(vs), 1448(w), 1348(m) and 1125(s).	3.38(3H,s,OCH ₃) at (C-3), 3.70(2H,m, methylene at C-3), 3.79(3H,s,COOCH ₃) and 4.17(1H,m, methine at C-2).
h-ii	2990(m), 2950(m), 2925(w), 2890(vw), 2820(m), 1740-1760(vs, unresolved doublet), 1455(w) and 1195(m).	3.48(3H,s,OCH ₃ at C-2), 3.59(2H,m, methylene at C-3), 3.78(3H,s,COOCH ₃ at C-2) and 4.30(1H,m, methine at C-2).

Contd.

i	2975(s),2825(m),a doublet at 1725(s) and 1710(vs),1180(m), 1137(s) and 1077(vs).	1.36(6H,s, two methyl groups attached to C-4),2.32 (3H,s,COCH ₃), 3.28 (3H,s,OCH ₃) and 4.32(1H,s methine at C-3).
j	3460(w),3090(w),3065(w),3030(w), 2825(m),1730(vs),1450(m) and 1100(s).	2.31(3H,s,COCH ₃), 3.15(3H,s,OCH ₃), 4.25(1H,d,J= 10Hz, methine at C-3),4.58(1H,d,J= 10Hz,C-4methine) and 7.36(5H,s, aromatic).
k	3040(m),2995(m),2940(s),2825(s), 1450(m),1352(m),1113(vs) and 1090(s).	3.22(3H,s,OCH ₃), 3.40(2H,m,CH ₂ Br), 4.32(1H,m, methine at C-2) and 7.30(5H,s, aromatic).
l	3052(m),3020(m),2920(m),2815(m), 1495(m),1455(s) and 1112(vs).	3.20(3H,s,OCH ₃),4.38(1H,d,J=8Hz,methine at C-1), 4.86(1H,d,J=8Hz, methine at C-2) and 6.99(10H,s, aromatic).
m	3080(w),3057(m),3025(m),2820(m), 1490(m),1450(s),1357(m),1113(s), 1105(s) and 1090(s).	3.15(3H,s,OCH ₃),4.54(1H,d,J=6.5 Hz, methine at C-1),4.88(1H,d,J=6.5 Hz, methine at C-2) and 7.25 (10H,s, aromatic).
n	2825(m),1562(s),1450(m),1350(s) and 1100(s).	3.13(3H,s,OCH ₃),4.79(1H,d,J= 10 Hz),5.91(1H,d,J= 10 Hz) and 7.38(5H,s, aromatic).
o-i	2910(vs,br),2855(m),2815(m), 1449(s),1370(s),1190(s),1180 (s),1120(vs) and 1090(vs)	1.50(8H,m, four methylene groups), 3.22(1H,m, methine at C-1),3.38(3H,s,OCH ₃) and 3.97(1H,m, methine at C-2).
o-ii	2940(vs),2860(s),2820(m), 1470(m),1445(s),1355(m),1167 (s),1118(s) and 1090(s).	1.83(8H,m, four methylene groups), 3.29(1H,m, methine at C-1),3.38(3H,s,OCH ₃) and 4.18(1H,m, methine at C-2).

vw=very weak, w=weak, m=medium, s=strong and vs=very strong.

*s=singlet, d=doublet, m=multiplet; Tetramethylsilane was used as internal reference.

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL RESULTS FOR SOME UNKNOWN COMPOUNDS (II)

Compound	Mol. formula	Found				Requires			
		C	H	Br	Cl	C	H	Br	Cl
II (d,e)	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrO ₂	50.19	5.20	27.32	—	50.13	5.26	27.87	—
II (f,g)	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrClO ₂	42.90	3.98	25.53	12.04	42.92	3.90	26.01	11.54
IIh (ii)	C ₅ H ₉ BrO ₂	30.48	4.63	40.03	—	30.45	4.56	40.60	—
II i	C ₇ H ₁₁ BrO ₂	40.20	6.62	38.77	—	40.19	6.22	38.27	—
II l	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ BrO	61.92	5.61	27.60	—	61.85	5.15	27.49	—

methanol whose S_N2 attack at either carbon leads to exclusive methoxybromination of the alkene and the net result becomes addition of the elements of methylhypobromite (CH₃OBr) to C=C bond. The ring-opening of the cyclic bromonium ion is solely dependent upon the nature of the alkene. It may open up at either carbon

of the symmetrically substituted alkene. In case of unsymmetrical alkenes, substantial ring opening will take place at the carbon bearing electron-donating substituent (s) capable of contributing stability to the incipient carbonium ion generated during the ring-opening process. Such bromonium ions are better termed as bromocarbenium ions wherein bromine is less associated to one carbon than to the other one in the three-membered ring. But unsymmetrical true bromonium ion should open up

at either carbon but to different extents. If the intermediate behaves like a true carbonium ion wherein bromine is not associated at all to one of the two carbons, it would become planar and methanol may attack from either site giving two diastereomers but only one positional isomer; also above room temperature some E₁-elimination product might possibly be obtained.

The present work deals only with the cases involving either true bromonium ion or bromocarbenium ion.

Stereochemistry

It is clear from Table 1 that *cis*-alkene gives *threo*-diastereomer and the *trans*-alkene affords *erythro*-diastereomer. In their nmr spectra the J-values for methine protons in *erythro*-diastereomer are found to be somewhat less than in the *threo*-diastereomer (Table 2)^{20,22}. The ir spectra for *threo*-diastereomer (II-1) and *erythro*-diastereomer (II-m) are found to be similar but not superimposable. Cyclic alkenes such as cyclohexene (I-o) afforded only one isomer i.e. *trans*-1-bromo-2-methoxycyclohexane (II o-i)^{2,10} showing the intervention of true bromonium ion intermediate.

The stereochemistry of methoxybromo adducts (II) was established by their dehydrobromination under E₂-

elimination conditions³¹ with representative compounds II (a + b, 1, m and o-i). A 51:49 mixture of the alkenes I (a and b) was prepared by our previously reported reaction³². The methoxybromination of the same mixture afforded a 51:49 mixture of II (a and b) in 95% yield. Their ratio in the crude sample was determined by the areas of integration in the nmr spectrum for the three protons of the ethereal methoxy group at C-3. When 51:49 mixture of II (a and b) was treated with potassium *tert*-butoxide in dry ether at room temperature for one week a mixture of the enol ethers V (a and b) was obtained in 73% overall yield in the relative ratio of 1:6.6 as determined by the areas of integration for the olefinic protons in the nmr spectrum of their crude sample. Their chemical shifts are assigned to be δ 5.53 and δ 5.14 in V (a and b) respectively. The stretching band for C=C in ir spectrum gets submerged with very strong and broad band for COOCH₃ group. Thus it is apparent that the ester Va is partially isomerising to the more stable ester Vb either during the reaction or its work-up.

Va ;	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
b ;	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOCH ₃	H
1 ;	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	C ₆ H ₅
m ;	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	H

The dehydrobromination of the *threo*-diastereomer (II-1) with potassium *tert*-butoxide in dry ether occurred readily in 5 hr at room temperature to afford *trans*-alkene (V-1)²⁷ whose glc analysis showed only one peak. Interestingly enough the dehydrobromination of the *erythro*-diastereomer (II-m) with potassium *tert*-butoxide in dry ether did not occur at all even after 7hr at 0° or 5hr at room temperature whereas similar E₂-dehydrobromination reactions under these conditions are reported³¹ to be complete in less than 30 min. This fact is attributed to energetically unfavourable eclipsing effect experienced in the transition state for dehydrobromination of the *erythro*-diastereomer (II-m). However, the dehydrobromination did occur at room temperature in one week to give the *cis*-alkene (V-m)²⁷. It showed only one peak on glc column C at 110°. However, on column D at 152° two peaks were observed possibly due to partial isomerisation of V-m to V-1. This proves the compounds II (1 and m) to be *threo*- and *erythro*-diastereomers respectively and consequently the methoxybromination to be *trans*- and stereospecific.

The methoxybromination of cyclohexene (I-o) also appears to be *trans*- and stereospecific. Thus if the stereochemistry of the bromoether (II o-ii) were *cis*- as shown in VI the dehydrobrominated product under E₂-elimination conditions would be expected to be 1-methoxycyclohexene (VII)^{28,29}. When the bromoether (II o-i) was treated with potassium *tert*-butoxide in dry dimethyl sulphoxide for 48 hrs at room

temperature and 2 hrs at 100°, only 3-methoxycyclohexene (V o-i) was indeed obtained. Its identity was established by superimposability of its retention time on glc columns B and E, ir and nmr spectra with that of an authentic sample prepared by refluxing *trans*-1,2-dibromocyclohexane (VIII)³³ with sodium methoxide in methanol for 9 hr²⁹. Surprisingly 3-methoxycyclohexene (V o-i) was found completely resistant to its isomerisation to the thermodynamically more stable isomer (VII)

when treated with potassium *tert*-butoxide in *tert*-butanol and dry dimethyl sulphoxide for 5 hr at 100°. Such a reluctance could be attributed to electrostatic repulsion between the electrons of the incipient carbanion generated at C-3 and unshared pair of electrons of oxygen in the methoxy group during the base-catalysed isomerisation of Vo-i to VII under the reaction conditions for dehydrobromination of IIo-ii. As depicted in IX, the approaching base will experience some electro-

static repulsion caused due to unshared pair of electrons of oxygen in methoxy group and also steric hindrance due to 1,3-diaxial steric interaction. Drastic reaction condition for elimination was, therefore, required to force the base to come in the vicinity of methoxy group. E₂-elimination, in this case, failed completely under mild reaction conditions.

Thus the results of E₂-elimination (Table 4) are quite consistent with *trans*- and stereospecific E₂-elimination of hydrobromide to afford alkenes (V).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were taken in carbon tetrachloride solution on Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer Model 237 (unless noted otherwise). NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 instrument in carbon tetrachloride. The gas liquid chromatographic analyses were carried out on Perkin-Elmer Gas Chromatograph Model 810 (flame ionisation detector) and on a hand built glc instrument (3000 ohm thermistor thermal conductivity detector). The following glc columns were used : Column A: 6 ft., 1/8" o.d., stainless steel, packed with 25% DC-560

silicone oil on 60-80 mesh chromosorb P; Column B: 6 ft., 1/8" o.d., stainless steel, packed with 10% 1,2,3-tris-(2-cyanoethoxy) propane (TCEP) on 60-80 mesh chromosorb P; Column C: 0.6 cm. i.d. x 210 cm., Pyrex U-tube, packed with 20% Hyvac. silicone grease on 60-80 mesh chromosorb P; Column D: 6 ft., 1/8" o.d., stainless steel, packed with 3% G.E. methyl silicone rubber (SE-30) on 60-80 mesh chromosorb P; and Column E: 50 ft., stainless steel capillary, packed with diethyleneglycol succinate (DEGS) x 0.02" o.d., s.s. support coated. Liquid compounds (II) were distilled under vacuum and solid compounds were readily crystallised from hot aqueous ethanol. The alkenes I (d and f) were prepared by Fisher's esterification method^{3,4}.

General Procedure for Methoxybromination of Alkenes (I)

To a magnetically-stirred suspension of 0.05 mole of the alkene (I) in 250 ml of methanol containing 0.06 mole of silver nitrate, or 0.03 mole of lead nitrate, or 0.03 mole of yellow lead oxide, was added a solution of 0.06 mole of bromine in 150 ml of methanol over a period of 0.5 to 1 hr. The temperature was maintained between -20° and room temperature depending on the nature of alkene. Stirring was continued for an additional 2 to 20 hr. The alkene (Ig) required 4 days. The precipitated silver or lead bromide was filtered off. The methanol was removed from the filtrate by distillation, the residue was leached with about 150 ml of ether and insoluble inorganic material was filtered off. The nitric acid generated *in situ*, when silver or lead nitrate was used as the trapping agent, was neutralised by treatment of the ethereal leachings with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The ethereal extract was washed with water and brine solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Filtration and evaporation of ether afforded the desired methoxybromination product. The solid products (II) were readily crystallised from hot aqueous ethanol while liquid products were distilled under vacuum.

In cases of methoxyiodination methanolic solution, of iodine was used instead of bromine. Silver nitrate was used as the only trapping agent. Lead nitrate or yellow lead oxide was ineffective.

The Reaction of a 51:49 Mixture of Methylcis-3-Phenylprop-2-enoate (Ia) and Methyl trans-3-Phenylprop-2-enoate (Ib) with Bromine in Methanol in the Presence of Yellow Lead Oxide.

A solution of 24.30g (0.152 mole) of bromine in 400 ml of methanol was added dropwise over a period of 1 hr to a magnetically-stirred suspension of 17.00g (0.076 mole) of a mixture of the alkenes I (a and b), prepared by the cyanide ion-catalysed reaction of 3-phenylprop-2-ynal with methanol^{3,5}, in 400 ml of methanol at room temperature. After 16 hr additional stirring at room temperature, the usual work-up of the reaction mixture afforded 20.00g (95%) yield. According to nmr, the crude product appeared to be a 51:49 mixture of the diastereomers II (a and b). Spectral data are presented in Table 2.

The Reaction of a 51:49 Mixture of Methyl threo-2-Bromo-3-methoxy-3-phenylpropanoate (IIa) and Methyl erythro-2-Bromo-3-methoxy-3-phenylpropanoate (IIb) with Potassium tert-Butoxide in dry Ether at Room Temperature.

To a magnetically-stirred solution of 18.45g (0.0675 mole) of a 51:49 mixture of the *threo*-diastereomer (IIa) and *erythro*-diastereomer (IIb) in 500 ml of dry ether in a 1-litre Erlenmeyer flask protected with a calcium chloride drying tube, was added 9.40g (0.084 mole) of potassium *tert*-butoxide in one portion. The reaction mixture developed immediately a light brown colour which finally turned to faint yellow. After one week magnetic-stirring at room temperature, the reaction mixture was worked up as usual to afford 9.52g (73%) yield of crude material, distilled, 8.54g, b.p. 83-98°(0.1 mm), According to the nmr spectrum of crude material it appeared to be a 1:6.6 mixture of the dehydrobrominated alkene V (a and b). Spectral data are presented in Table 4.

trans-1-Methoxy-1,2-diphenylethylene (V-1)

To a magnetically-stirred solution of 2.91g (0.01 mole) of *threo*-1-bromo-2-methoxy-1,2-diphenylethane (II-1) in 75 ml of dry ether in a 125 ml Erlenmeyer flask protected with a calcium chloride drying tube, was added rapidly 1.35g (0.012 mole) of potassium *tert*-butoxide and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 5 hr. The usual work-up of the reaction mixture afforded 1.30g (61%) yield of crude dehydrobrominated *trans*-alkene (V-1). When left in refrigerator for overnight, it solidified. Recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 51°-51.5° (lit.^{2,7} m.p. 51.5°-52°). Spectral data are presented in Table 4.

cis-1-Methoxy-1,2-diphenylethylene (V-m)

To a magnetically-stirred solution of 2.91g (0.01 mole) of *erythro*-1-bromo-2-methoxy-1,2-diphenylethane (II-m) in 75 ml of dry ether in a 125 ml Erlenmeyer flask protected with a calcium chloride drying tube was added rapidly 1.35g (0.012 mole) of potassium *tert*-butoxide and stirring was continued at room temperature for one week. Insoluble material was filtered, the filtrate was washed with cold water (2x50 ml) and 50 ml of brine solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. Removal of ether from the filtrate afforded 1.30g (61%) of crude product (V-m). Its glc analysis on column D at 152° showed two peaks of about equal area. However only one peak was observed on preparative glc column C at 110°. The alkene V-m possibly might have isomerised to V-1 on column D. It is also known that V-m isomerises to V-1 by heating at 203° for 3 hr^{2,7}. Therefore, the spectral data were recorded for only crude sample which are presented in Table 4.

3-Methoxycyclohexene (V o-i)

To a magnetically-stirred solution of 8.50g (0.044 mole) of *trans*-1-bromo-2-methoxycyclohexane (II o-i) in 20 ml of dry dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) at room temperature was added 5.60g (0.05 mole) of potassium

TABLE 4—DEHYDROBROMINATED PRODUCTS (v)

Compound	%Yield	B.P°.(mm)	I.R Spectra (cm ⁻¹)	N.M.R. Spectra (δ)
Va ^{25, 26}	73	83-98/0.1	3050(vw), 2948(m), 2825(m), 1705(s), 1490(m), 1436(m), 1380(m), 1156(vs) and 1115 (vs).	3.68(s, OCH ₃), 3.9(s, COOCH ₃) 5.57(s, olefinic) and 7.38 (s, aromatic).
Vb ²⁶				
VI ²⁷	61	Solid, m.p. 51-51.5	3075(vw), 3050(m), 3015(m), 2835(m), 1631(m), 1597(m), 1485(m), 1446(s), 1194(m), and 1060(vs).	3.48(3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.98(1H, s, olefinic), 7.14(5H, m, aromatic at C-2) and 7.50(5H, m, aromatic at C-1).
Vm ²⁷	61	liquid	3075(vw), 3050(m), 3010(m), 2965(m), 2830(m), 1632(m), 1598(m), 1496(m), 1462(m), 1445(m), 1370(m), 1195(s) and 1120 (vs).	3.52 3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.77(1H, s, olefinic), 6.98(5H, m, aromatic at C-2) and 7.19(5H, m, aromatic at C-1).
Vo-i ^{28, 29}	90	65-67/65-66	3030(m), 2980(m), 2945(s), 2820(m), 1650(w), 1450(m), 1395(m), 1350(m), 1188(m), 1105(vs), 927(s) and 715(m).	1.66(4H, m, homoallylic), 1.96(2H, m, allylic), 3.27(3H, s, OCH ₃), 3.67 (1H, m, methine at C-3) and 5.77 (2H, d, J=1. 5Hz, olefinic).
VII ³⁰		138-142	1675 (C=C-OCH ₃).	1.57(4H, m, homoallylic), 2.00 (4H, m, allylic), 3.42(3H, OCH ₃) and 4.50(1H, m, olefinic).

tert-butoxide. The reaction mixture became warm and dark-brown immediately, then slowly cooled to room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 48 hr at room temperature and then heated on a steam cone for 2 hr at 100°. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool, poured into 300 ml of cold water contained in a separatory funnel and extracted with ether (5x100 ml); the ethereal extract was washed with cold water (5x100 ml) to remove all DMSO and finally with 100 ml of brine solution. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and removal of ether from the filtrate afforded 4.87g (99.5%) yield of the crude 3-methoxycyclohexene (V o-i), distilled to get 4.50g of the pure product, b.p. 65°-67° (65-66 mm), lit^{28, 29} b.p. 65°-67.5° (65 mm). The ir spectrum was recorded in carbon tetrachloride solution on Perkin-Elmer 337 using potassium bromide of 0.1 mm thickness. Spectral data are presented in Table 4.

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